

GREEN PERFORMANCE AND EMPLOYEES' CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR: EXAMINING THE ROLE OF EMPLOYEES' PRIDE AND COMMITMENT.

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6553247](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6553247)

ABSTRACT:

Promoting positive behavior of employees (such as organizational citizenship behavior - OCB) has become a crucial factor that determines the success of all the firms in general, in tourism industry in particular. The purpose of this study is to examine the mechanism of employees' perceptions of green performance of hotels influence their OCB with the serial mediating effects of psychology (perceived pride) and emotion (affective commitment) of employees working in the hotel. A conceptual research model is developed and then empirically examined using PLS - SEM. The study data was collected from 209 employees working in hotel at Moc Chau national tourism area (Vietnam) via a questionnaire survey. The results show that there is a positive correlation between employees' perception of green performance of their hotel and their OCB. Interestingly, employees' perceived pride and affective commitment act as serial mediators in the relationship correlation between employees' perception of green performance of their hotel and their OCB. This study offers new insight for researchers and managers in the hospitality industry in term of "go green" tendency.

Keywords: *Green performance, tourist, citizenship behavior, perceive pride, affective commitment*

Paper type: **Research paper**

INTRODUCTION

Abraham Maslow stated about the subject of human motivation: human nature is good, when giving people safety and affection, they will also gain affection in their psychology, emotion and behavior (Lowry & Lowry, 1973). Assurance of employee commitments is a major concern in human resource development and organizational development. Increasingly, modern executives are focusing more on attracting, training, and increasing the loyalty of competent employees to maintain a competitive edge for firms (Baumann, Hoadley, Hamin, & Nugraha, 2017; Boğan & Dedeoğlu, 2020). The modern environment is full of economic uncertainty, rapid change, continued globalization, increasing competition and the rise of the mobile millennium serving as the foundation and potential driving force for increasing attention and focus on employee commitment from both students and academics. The current environment is changing rapidly with continuous globalization, increasing economic uncertainty, and increasing competition. The rise and growth of the mobile network serve as a driving force and an important foundation for focusing on employee engagement (Albrecht, Bakker, Gruman, Macey, & Saks, 2015; Nazir & Islam, 2017). Research by Risher (2014) demonstrates that a poor attitude, mentality or feeling about the business can reduce employee's commitment to the organization (Risher, 2014). In the same vein, Alvino (2014) indicated that employees' overtime behaviors and work performance are affected by factors such as emotional attachment and commitment of employees to the organization (Alvino, 2014). Davies (2015), while highlighting the re-focus of corporations on emotional commitment and happiness, stated that "this is the unified philosophy of the 21st century manager: Every worker can be better, physically, mentally and output" highlighting the importance of focusing on emotional commitments. Each worker can become better mentally, in their health and performance.

Currently, businesses are facing many difficulties due to low rubber prices leading to more fierce competition. In addition to traditional solutions such as increasing capital, investing in science and technology, the policy makers have policies to support... actively increasing the number of human resources of the company is also one of the key factors to increase competitiveness. Stemming from the above issues, this study contributes to better understanding the importance of organizational citizenship to the organization's work efficiency, as well as contributing to improving the quality of employees (Ong, Mayer, Tost, & Wellman, 2018). OCB research helps company managers to have a complete and comprehensive view of their employees to come up with the right policies and measures to encourage innovation and motivate employees. This is an important basis for improving productivity and working efficiency of employees, ensuring fairness, reliability, increasing employees' cohesion with the organization.

Tourism which is one of the most developed economic sectors recent years, has contributed a lot of works for the economy of almost all countries in over the world. Economists indicated that the development of society and economy stimulates the high and diversifying demand of customers for the tourist services such as natural tourism, psychical tourism, cultural tourism...

For this reason, many countries have built a tourism – based country development strategy for the future. Vietnam which is a developing country in the Southeast of Asia, has marked to the world with high economic growth rates in the recent years. With the openness and development policy of Vietnamese government from 1986, Vietnam economy has been developed in an impression manner. For instance, the GDP per capita has increased annually with USD 2,715 (2019) in comparison with 96,343 (1989) as the number of World Bank. In term of tourism, Vietnam is a country with very rich and diverse tourism resources, many natural landscapes, long and beautiful beaches as well as many unspoiled natural areas. Specifically, many places have been recognized as world natural heritage such as Son Doong cave, Ha Long Bay... Therefore, green tourism (sustainable tourism) is not only a phenomenon but also an urgent requirement for the country's sustainable development to meet the needs of the times.

Finally, this study is based on the theory of social identity theory and selection of the natural tourism scene in the Moc Chau national tourism area. That means that the main aim of this study is the link between green practices and OCB. Because this area is one of the most famous natural tourism destinations in Vietnam, it attracts a lot of hotel tourists every year. With the provincial government's sustainable tourism development strategy, the manner of hotel staff affects the better service and quality of service. Therefore, in order to evaluate the effectiveness and contribute to documentation and practice, this study attempts to answer the following research questions:

Firstly, to what extent does the employee's perception of green practices influence their OCB?

Secondly, to what extent does employees' perceived pride and affective commitment affect green practices and OCB?

Thirdly, how does employees' perceived pride and commitment affect the relationship between their perception of green practices and their OCB?

This current article is arranged as follow: Following the introduction are the fundamental theories and hypothesis proposes. The third part is the data collection section, which continues with the data analysis section. This article concludes with conclusion and discussion.

2. BACKGROUND THEORY AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Green Practice and OCB

Green practice is the activity of environmental commitments including: environmental protection, waste treatment, corporate social responsibility (CSR)... Nowadays, products and services related to the environment which are currently in serious need of society (Namkung & Jang, 2017). To solving the problems, hotel managements have to understand and practice this issue well in practice (Han, Hsu, Lee, & Sheu, 2011). In addition without issues related to customers, the success of a green hotel depending on the personal beliefs and daily actions of the staff. Individual environmental standards explain variance in hotels, but green organizational climates explain variance between hotels and control with the effect of

individual environmental standards on individual environmental behavior (Chia-Jung & Pei-Chun, 2014)

Smith, Organ & Near (1983) showed OCB is personal, voluntary, non-direct or explicitly binding behavior is recognized by rewarding the organization's system but this drives the organization's performance (Smith, Organ, & Near, 1983). OCB depicts such spontaneous employee behavior promoting the efficient and effective functioning of the organization. These specialties include: author, owner and goodwill. In 1988, Organ again re-clarified the nature of the OCB as "a voluntary, personal behavior that is not directly or explicitly recognized in regular rewarding activities but has the effect of promoting effective activities of the organization. This behavior does not stem from the required orders, the characteristics of the job or agreement in the job. Sandra and Morrison's research's results showed that employers are disappointed because their employees do not meet their duties when their employees work after 18 months. The research also showed that employees are less able to express their civic behavior. The relationship between employee and employer is in part based on trust (Robinson & Morrison, 1995).

According to the social identity theory, staffs are aware of their organization's effort development defining clearly by emphasizing environmental orientation, they feel higher valued than working for an eco-friendly company (Gavrilović & Maksimović, 2018). In other words, an employee's positive self-image by adjusting their identity to the organization (E. M. Lee, Park, Rapert, & Newman, 2012). Furthermore, (Cherrington & England, 1980) pointed out that work demonstrates value to individuals through psychology. According to social identity theory, employees perceive their organization's efforts to develop emotion and have the ability to be clearly defined by emphasizing environmental orientation, when they feel more valued than when working for an environmentally friendly company (Flory, Bonet, Guillon, & Cezanne, 2014). In other words, green practice enhances an employee's positive self-image by adjusting their identity to the organization (Lee et al., 2012). According to research by Kamal Manaktola, Vinnie Jauhari (2007), all individuals tend to develop the values they receive sustainably, then formulate and ultimately act on green practices. According to Trang et al, (2018), the attributes of a green hotel in particular which are 5 aspects: customer benefits, energy efficiency, water saving, recycling policy and green identity has a positive effect on the value and profitability of environmental attitudes, thereby enhancing the intention to take eco-friendly actions and visiting a green hotel, at the same time, environmental households (Trang, Lee, & Han, 2019). From these evidence, this research hypothesis that:

H1: Employees' perception of green practice has positive impact on their perceived pride

Recently, (E. M. Lee, Park, & Lee, 2013) researching staff casinos found a positive relationship between green practice and organizational trust. Lee et al. (2012) used the views of food service employee in Korea to experimentally examine the effects of CSR on work attitudes and behaviors (L. Lee & Chen, 2018). Affective commitment (AC) describes the employee's affective attachment to the organization, stemming from accepting the organization's values. The hotel is a too familiar concept, it is where the service business stores accommodation,

catering services and other complementary services... While green hotels provide services to diners on a guaranteed basis and environmental protection. For a society where environmental pollution is a problem in all countries around the world, the "greening up of hotels" model completely raises awareness and increases attitudes to feel positive about the place there. As (Matzler & Renzl, 2006) noted that the hotel employees' low awareness of green practices needs further improvement to perfect the system. Values (reward benefits of the program) and sentiment (feeling attached to the brand) from research by (Spreitzer, 1995) and restrictions from international treaties and individual institutional commitment to move green in the hospitality industry from (Graci & Dodds, 2008) provides fair value. Employees who believe that their organization pursues green program by supporting eco-friendly practices is proud of being part of the organization, thus leading to a more positive working attitude. An empirical study by (E. M. Lee et al., 2013) revealed that employees have the ability to show positive working attitudes (e.g. job satisfaction) when they see moral activities. Similarly, (Carnahan, Kryscynski, & Olson, 2017) pointed out that an organization's ethical environment affects employee's job satisfaction. Therefore, we believe that green practice fosters a strong ethical environment, makes employees feel good about themselves and thus increases the motivation to work hard by demonstrating a sense of commitment to organization. An empirical study by (Brammer, He, & Mellahi, 2015) revealed that employees are capable of displaying a positive work attitude (e.g. job satisfaction) when they see a company behave morally. Therefore, we believe that green practice fosters a strong ethical environment, makes employees feel good about themselves and thus increases their motivation to work hard by demonstrating a commitment to cohesion, bundle with the firms. From these evidence, this research hypothesis that:

H2: Employees' perception of green practice has positive impact on their affective commitment.

Tyler (1999) suggested that people become more emotionally engaged with an organization in the extent that their membership in the organization contributes to an organization positive social identity (Tyler, 1999). More specifically, it is argued that the valuable organizational characteristics can be considered a source of organizational pride for the individual employees, creating satisfaction and commitment to the organization. , and can therefore be an important source of employee collaborative behavior (Ghitulescu, 2018; Shen & Benson, 2016). Accordingly, empirical research in organizations has determined that organizational pride predicts individual employees' psychological attachment and motivation. The organization's environmental policy helps employees gain confidence in the environment. Environmental training is an essential element of employees' environmental beliefs. Employees' environmental beliefs lead to citizen's behavior toward the environment. Supporting the environment enhances the impact of staff's environmental beliefs on OCB, which is the fact that hotel staff say they are increasingly engaged in eco-friendly citizenship behavior as their environmental confidence increases (W. G. Kim, McGinley, Choi, & Agmapisarn, 2020). In addition, green training positively affects the organization's environmental and behavioral commitment, and the cognitive behavioral control completely mediates the association of hotel staff (Hwang & Lyu, 2020). From these evidence, this research hypothesis that:

H3: Employees' perception of green practice positively related to OCB.

2.2. Perceived pride

Pride is a complex human emotion resulting from the positive influence of the perceived value of an object or person with which the object is closely related. Pride can be either an introverted or an extrovert emotion depending on the context. Pride can be expressed through many different means. The non-verbal representation of pride can serve as a means of sending a functional signal, automatically perceived to be worth, status or achievement.

Tyler (1999) suggested that people should become more emotionally engaged with an organization, to the extent that their membership in this organization contributes to a positive social identity (Tyler, 1999). More specifically, it is suggested that the valuable organizational characteristics can be considered as a source of organizational pride for individual employees, creating satisfaction and commitment to the business and this can be an important reason for the employee's cooperative behavior with the organization (W. G. Kim et al., 2020). According to Tyler & Blader, 2000 organizational pride will predict the psychological attachment as well as work motivation for individual employees (Tyler & Blader, 2003). From these evidence, this study suggests that:

H4: Employees' perceived pride has a positive effect on their affective commitment.

A model describing employee attitudes that mediate the relationship between employee voluntariness and their behavior (Breitsohl & Ehrig, 2017). The model suggests that workplace attitudes such as awareness, pride, and job satisfaction can mediate the relationships between employee volunteerism and realistic work behaviors, present tasks, citizenship behavior of the organization and counterproductive working behavior. Furthermore, Glavas & Kelly (2014) suggested that perceived organizational support (POS) can enhance the impact of employee volunteering on an organization's results such as satisfaction at work, organizational identity and organizational commitment that explain the relationship between CSR perceptions (including green practices) and the organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) (Glavas & Kelley, 2014).

Organizational pride refers to a member's appreciation of the integrity of the organization they belong to (Tyler & Blader, 2003). Perceived pride is defined as “the degree to which individuals experience a sense of excitement and self-esteem arising from their organizational membership” (Boğan & Dedeoğlu, 2020). Organizational commitment and organizational pride expressing expected responses to these perceptions are consistent with the arguments of social exchange and social identity theory (Brown, McHardy, McNabb, & Taylor, 2011). Furthermore, according to the social identity and social exchange statement, on the success of the organization based on the employee's willingness to contribute, this willingness is influenced by perceived pride and a sense of organizational commitment. They will be motivated to do their best for the good of the organization, and thus demonstrate broader performance (Blader & Tyler, 2009; Boğan & Dedeoğlu, 2020).

Previous documents suggest that perceived pride can be a psychological mechanism that can combine an organization's voluntary meaning and civic behavior. When employees feel meaningful at work, they tend to be for the benefit of the organization that collaborate with colleagues. In addition, they can engage in civic behaviors beyond the level required by their organization. Hence, this study hypothesizes that:

H5: Employees' perceived pride has positive effect on OCB.

2.3. Affective commitment

According to Meyer & Allen (1991), emotional commitment is the employee's emotional attachment to the organization, identification and participation in the organization (Meyer & Allen, 1991). This can be demonstrated through the sharing of values, the desire to continue working for the benefit of the business. In the study of Meyer and Herscovitch (2001), there are still many confusion and disagreement about the definition of commitment and its influence on behavior (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001). Emotional commitment can be understood as an individual's emotional attachment to an organization expressed through an individual's identity with participation in the organization (E. M. Lee et al., 2013; Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001). These research showed that individuals who show a lack of positive attitudes towards enterprises in the first week of work tend to leave the organization. In addition, they found organizational dissatisfaction as a precursor to the ultimate revenue change. Besides, the disorganization is the result of a degree of affective commitment.

Rhoades et al (2001) studied the relationship between work experience, organizational support awareness, affective commitment (AC), and employee turnover and found relationships between negative relationship between organizational support awareness (helping the organization be perceived) and subsequent voluntary employee turnover due to AC in retail and livestock workers (Rhoades, Eisenberger, & Armeli, 2001). Favorable working conditions operate over POS to increase AC, thereby reducing employee withdrawals and emotional commitment and self-esteem are the main drivers of citizenship behavior (Norton, Parker, Zacher, & Ashkanasy, 2015).

Commitment is considered an important factor in retaining talented employees, encouraging employees to participate in activities for the organization and thus enhancing employee commitment is a goal. Managers are concerned for the long-term and stable development of the organization (Cetin, Gürbüz, & Sert, 2015). Other researchers showed that organizational trust and emotional commitment are the complete mediation of the relationship between commitment and the citizenship behavior of the organization (Turker, 2009; Wang, Tong, Takeuchi, & George, 2016). Emotional commitment is a topic that attracts many researchers because many aspects need to be tested and exploited. From these evidence, this study hypothesizes that:

H6: Affective commitment has positive impact on OCB.

H7: The relationship between employees' green performance and their OCB is serial mediated by perceived pride and affective commitment

In conclusion, we can depict the proposed research model as follow:

Figure 1. Research model

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Questionnaire design

To test the proposed hypothesis, this research utilizes the questionnaire survey method to collect the data. Participants are employees who work in the hotels in Moc Chau NTA. The authors selected this kind of respondents because they have well understood the activities of the hotels wherein they work for. So that they can apprehend the green performance activities of their hotels which in turn stimulate their positive or negative emotion towards their hotels. This research applied scales from previous studies and adapted to fit the new context of green tourism in Vietnam. All scales are in the form of Likert-5 which range from 1 representing strongly disagree to 5 representing strongly agree.

Wherein, employees' perception of green performance includes of 8 items adopted from (S.-H. Kim & Choi, 2013), one of the items is "Using reusable utensils rather than disposable ones". Employees' perceived pride about the hotels composed of 3 items adapted from (Turban, Lau, Ngo, Chow, & Si, 2001) in which one of the items is "I am proud of being a member of my hotel". Employees' affective commitment includes of 6 items adapted from (Rhoades et al., 2001), one of the items is "I feel a strong sense of belonging to my hotel". Finally, employees' citizenship behavior is adapted from (Yang & Wei, 2018) which composes of 6 items, one example is "Helps others even though there is no formal request". To have a more consistent questionnaire, we applied back – translation technique by specialists in English and business management. That means the original items in English version were translated into Vietnamese and then translated back to English, the specialists in English and business management compared the two versions and modified to have a draft version. To test the suitability of the questionnaire, this draft version is tested and checked with 15 employees who

work in the hotels at Moc Chau NTA in a pilot test and then the final version of questionnaire was determined.

3.2. Data collection

The main aim of this research is to evaluate the organizational citizenship behavior of employees who work in a hotel where practicing well the green performance. So the population for this research is all the employees who are working in Moc Chau NTA. Moc Chau NTA, belonging to Moc Chau district, Son La province, 180 km from Hanoi, 120 km from Son La city, is approved by the Prime Minister on the Planning as a national tourist area in May. 11/2014. These are 2 mountainous districts located on the limestone plateau of the Northwest region with an average altitude of more than 1,000 m above sea level. There are 12 minority ethnics live together in Moc Chau district with abundant cultures such as clothes, specialties, foods as well as house on stilts. That means Moc Chau NTA has both natural tourism resources and humanity resources which is the basement for develop sustainable tourist industry.

Figure 2. Map of Moc Chau district, Son La province (Vietnam)

We applied a simple random sampling method through questionnaire survey with employees of hotel at this area. The questionnaire consisted of 23 main questions, so according to (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 1998) the minimum sample size would be 115 questionnaires. To collect the most appropriate responses, the research team selected 11 homestays at Moc Chau NTA and 20 respondents for each homestay. This study was deployed

in one month. Finally, the result has a total of 209 valid questionnaires collected after the survey, means the rate about 95%. The demographics of the respondents is depicted as follows:

Table 1. Demographic information of respondents

Factors	Component	Amount	%
Gender	Male	101	48.3
	Female	108	51.7
Age	Under 25	37	17.7
	25 – 35	73	34.9
	35 - 45	73	34.9
	Over 45	26	12.4
Income (VND/month)	Under 5 million	17	8.1
	5 – 10 million	122	58.4
	10 – 15 million	53	25.4
	Over 15 million	17	8.1
Education	High school	110	52.6
	College	13	6.2
	University	78	37.3
	Other	8	3.8

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

This study applied the PLS-SEM path model to test hypotheses through Smart PLS 2.0 software (Hair Jr, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2016). Compared with other empirical analytical methods, the proposed research model is the most suitable for this method because it focuses on predicting and explaining the complex relationship between the variables in the model and consistent with the small research sample (n = 209). Furthermore, it can explain a relationship of reflective construct and formative construct. Moreover, this research attempts to clarify the serial mediating effects of employees' perceived pride and affective commitment in the relationship between green perception and employees' organizational citizenship behavior.

4.1. Scales measurement evaluation

To evaluate the scales, the current research used Cronbach's alpha ($C\alpha$), composite reliability (CR) and average extracted variance (AVE). In which, the minimum loading factor is 0.61 and the highest is 0.88, satisfying the cut-off value 0.5. Besides, values of $C\alpha$ ranging from 0.71 to 0.85 and values of CR ranging from 0.84 to 0.89 are both greater than the level 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). These numbers proved the reliability of the scales satisfying the requirements. In addition, AVE values from 0.54 to 0.63 both satisfy cut – off value of 0.5 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), indicating that the convergence value is satisfactory (see Table 2).

Table 2. Measurement model evaluation

Variables	AVE	CR	$C\alpha$
Green practice perception	0.56	0.86	0.80
OCB	0.58	0.89	0.85
Perceived pride	0.69	0.87	0.78
Affective commitment	0.63	0.84	0.71

To test discriminant validity, this research first used the AVE value of each variable in the correlation to other variables (the Fornell - Larcker criteria). Then, the analytical results showed that the square root of AVE is greater than the correlation coefficient with other variables, demonstrating that the scales ensure discriminant validity (see **Table 3**).

Table 3. Construct AVE correlation

	GP	PP	AC	OCB
GP	1	0	0	0
PP	0.56	1	0	0
AC	0.62	0.79	1	0
OCB	0.47	0.58	0.69	1

4.2. Evaluation of structural model

After evaluating the scales by testing reliability, convergence and discriminant validity, the authors applied the PLS-SEM model to test the relationship of variables using SmartPLS software. The results of the relationships are shown in Figure 2

Figure 3. PLS testing results

The results of data analysis show that employees’ perception of green performance of hotels has positive effect on OCB ($\beta = 0.504$; $p < 0.001$, $t\text{-value} = 6.61$). Besides, employees’ perception of green performance of hotels positively impact on employees’ perceived pride towards the hotel ($\beta = 0.58$; $p < 0.001$, $t\text{-value} = 8.09$), as well as on employees’ affective commitment ($\beta = 0.426$; $p < 0.001$, $t\text{-value} = 4.24$). Employees perceived pride has positive effect on their affective commitment ($\beta = 0.225$; $p < 0.01$, $t\text{-value} = 2.49$), on OCB ($\beta = 0.306$; $p < 0.001$, $t\text{-value} = 4.82$). Finally, employees’ affective commitment positively effect on OCB ($\beta = 0.20$; $p < 0.001$, $t\text{-value} = 2.54$). These evidence confirmed that hypothesis H1, H2, H3, H4, H5 and H6 are supported.

To test the serial mediating effect of employees’ perceived pride and affective commitment in the relationship between green performance and tourist loyalty, a mediation model was built (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988) with PROCESS v3.3 by Hayes (Hayes, 2009). The testing results are showed as follow.

Table 4. Mediating effect testing

Direct effect of X on Y

Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	
	.0903	.0103	8.7472	.0000	.0699	.1106

Indirect effect(s) of X on Y:

Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI	
TOTAL	.0160	.0093	-.0013	.0355

Ind1	.0053	.0059	-.0063	.0173
Ind2	.0098	.0060	-.0003	.0234
Ind3	.0009	.0010	-.0009	.0032

Indirect effect key:

Ind1 OCB	->	PP	->	GP		
Ind2 OCB	->	AC	->	GP		
Ind3 OCB	->	PP	->	AC	->	GP

In **Table 4**, employees' perception of green performance of hotel has a significant impact on OCB ($\beta = 0.0903$, $p < 0.001$) in the direct model. The influence of employees' perception of green performance of hotel decreased in the indirect model 1 with employees' perceived pride acting as a mediator ($\beta = 0.0053$; $p < 0.001$, [-.0063, .0173]). In the same vein with indirect model 2 with the mediating role of employees' affective commitment ($\beta = 0.0098$; $p < 0.001$, [-.0003, .0234]). Especially, the results showed both employees' perceived pride and affective commitment influence on the relationship between employees' perception of green performance of hotel and OCB as the serial mediators ($\beta = 0.0009$; $p < 0.001$, [-.0009, .0032]). This evidence confirmed the hypothesis 8.

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In the modern life, human needs are more and more increasing, not only at a basic level as before but also at a higher level. They need to rest after stressful working hours and they want to travel to go back with natural mother. That stimulates the development of green tourism in all over the world. Besides, employees serving in the hotels contribute as a main factor that satisfy their tourists. So that in the manager perspective, it is necessary to understand how mechanism of employee behavior to have suitable solutions. This research is among the research that attempt to answer this question by focusing on the organizational citizenship behavior of employees who work in the hotels in Moc Chau NTA (Vietnam).

Specifically, this study attempt to clarify the employees' perceptions of hotel green practice performances, thereby assessing and examining its role in the correlation with their OCB with the mediating roles of perceived pride and affective commitment. Research shows that employees have their own point of view in term of the hotels' green performance which include of 8 items related to four group such as energy efficiency, water conservation, recycling and clean air (S.-H. Kim & Choi, 2013). In which, one example of recycling is "Using reusable utensils rather than disposable ones", of water conservation is "Landscaping with native plants to minimize water consumption", of energy efficiency is "Using Energy Star-rated equipment" and clean air is "Using environmentally preferable cleaning products". The evidence confirm that employees have well knowledge about the green performance of hotels in general.

In addition, the current research also clarifies the relationship between employees' perception of hotel green practices and their perceived pride towards the hotel ($\beta = 0.58$; $p < 0.001$, $t\text{-value} = 8.09$). That means the more their working hotel perform the green activities, the more they feel pride towards their hotel with relatives and with other people. The evidence also show that the green performance of hotel strongly influence on the pride of employees with $\beta = 0.58$. Moreover, previous scholars asserted that nowadays, the positive emotion is very importance determining the quality of all relationship in the society. Specifically, if employees have good emotion with their organization, they have certainly good attitude, behaviors and actions. It is a very importance thing that organization need to consider. This evidence also contributes to the literature in the field by filling the research gaps as proposed by previous researchers such as (Oo, Jung, & Park, 2018).

Besides, this research also explores the influence of employees' perception of green performance of hotels on employees' affective commitment ($\beta = 0.426$; $p < 0.001$, $t\text{-value} = 4.24$). This means when employees perceive the practice of green activities in their hotel, their commitment and retention to work in their hotels is in a higher level. Nowadays, retention employees in the organization is more and more important especially employees whose knowledge, ability and capability are good. This is a contribution to the tourist literature by filling the call of deeper examining the relationship between green performance and employees commitments such as (Norton et al., 2015; Wombacher & Felfe, 2017).

In the same vein, this research confirms the crucial role of employees' perception of green performance of hotels has positive effect on OCB ($\beta = 0.504$; $p < 0.001$, $t\text{-value} = 6.61$). As mentioned by previous scholars, employees' OCB is very important for the firms because it stimulates employees behaving as a part of the firm. But previous research also showed the OCB mechanism of employees is "under-estimated" (Ong et al., 2018) that need to deeper research, especially in the correlation with corporate social responsibility in the hospitality industry (Boğan & Dedeoğlu, 2020). This research indicated that employees' perception of green performance of hotels has directly positive effect on OCB. Moreover, this research also examines the mediating role of employees' perceived pride and affective commitment in this relationship.

To test the serial mediation of employees' perceived pride and affective commitment in the relationship between employees' perception of green performance of hotels and OCB, this research created a mediation model and applied PROCESS v3.3 by Hayes. The results showed that these two factors contribute as the serial mediation in the relationship of GP and OCB ($\beta = 0.0009$; $p < 0.001$, $[-.0009, .0032]$). This finding is a new in the field because as our knowledge to date, there is no research that examining these factors as the serial mediation between GP and OCB. This evidence fill the call of research by previous scholars such as (Boğan & Dedeoğlu, 2020).

Beside theoretical contribution, this research also has some managerial contribution to managers and policy makers.

Firstly, this research suggests that hotel managers need to understand the importance of the “green” factor by performing green practice activities in the hospitality and tourist industry. Because this factor has a direct effect on employees’ behavior, especially their OCB. Scholars pointed out that employee citizenship bring a lot of competitive advantage to the firm, employees not only retain working in the firms but also better serve their customers and work more efficiently. Nowadays, employee retention is very important that determine the success of all the firm, if the employees turn to the competitors working, that is really a terrible thing of the firm.

Secondly, this research indicates the important role of green performance in the psychology of employees who work in the firm. Specifically, the more employee perceive the green performance of hotel, the more positive psychological state (perceived pride towards the hotel) they have. So that employees will be very pride with other people when working in a firm that practice well the green activities. Managers of hotel in particular and all firms in general need to know this mechanism to have suitable solutions in the reality.

Thirdly, in the same vein, this research indicates the important role of green performance in the emotion of employees who work in the firm. Specifically, the more employee perceive the green performance of hotel, the more positive emotion (affective commitment) they have. Managers need to know this mechanism to have suitable solutions in the practice. Previous research also showed the importance of emotional state of employees in the relationship with their work creativity and productivity.

Fourthly, this research found the relation between psychology and emotion of employees by proposing the relationship between employees pride and their commitment with the firm. Positive emotion is crucial for the employees in the firm that stimulate them to be more productive and efficient in their work which in turn satisfy customer. Managers who know this relationship can apply well in their firms that can lead to a lot of competitive advantages to the firms.

Finally, the current research provides some contribution in terms of serial mediation of pride perception and commitment in the relationship between green practice and OCB. That means green practice can stimulate the OCB of employees by pride perception and affective commitment independently and both of these two factors. Managers know this mechanism can have solutions to improve the productivity of their employees, as well as their employees’ OCB.

Even the theoretical and practical contributions, this research still has some limitations. First, this research only collected the self – administered data from employees who work in homestay services in Moc Chau national tourism area, which may lead to incomplete and unrepresentative employees in other firms. Further research could expand the investigated area to have a more complete and comprehensive research sample. Second, the current research did not mention some of the variables that could moderate these relationships, such as gender, income, age, and education level. This suggests further research could clarify and give a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between green performance and employees’

behavior. This research did not examine the role of trust because trust and commitment is vastly research together. Moreover, future studies could also propose new factors to enrich knowledge on this topic in the current competitive context.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Ministry of Education and Training, Vietnam (Grant agreement number B2019-TTB-09).

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